

A fluorescent probe for the detection of clorprenaline and its analytical application

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Abstract : Clorprenaline (CLP) is non-fluorescent in aqueous solution, so we used the fluorescent complex cucurbit[7]uril-palmatine (CB[7]-PAL), as a fluorescent probe to detect CLP. The CB[7]-PAL probe exhibited high fluorescence in aqueous solution, which was quenched in the presence of CLP. Based on the significant quenching of the supramolecular complex fluorescence intensity, a new spectrofluorimetric method with high sensitivity and selectivity was developed to determine CLP in aqueous solution. A good linear correlation was obtained between the fluorescence quenching values (ΔF) and the CLP concentrations from $0.016 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ to $2.0 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$, with detection limit as low as $0.0053 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$. The proposed method was successfully applied to determine CLP in its pharmaceutical dosage forms with good precision and accuracy. The association constants of the complexes formed between the host and the guest were also determined. The competing reaction and the supramolecular interaction mechanisms between CLP and PAL as they fight for occupancy of the CB[7] cavity were studied using spectrofluorimetry, ^1H NMR, and molecular modeling calculations.

Keywords : Clorprenaline, cucurbit[7]uril, palmatine, fluorescent probe.

Introduction

Cucurbit[n]urils (CB[n]s, $n = 5-8, 10$, Fig. 1) are cyclic methylene-linked glycoluril oligomers. They are annular shaped with two identical carbonyl-fringed portals¹⁻³. Their structural characteristics enable them to form stable complexes with a variety of guest molecules in aqueous solution. Accordingly, this CB[n]s property demonstrates their broad utility in molecular recognition and self-assembly studies. Numerous organic drugs and biologically relevant molecules have been encapsulated by

CB[n]s^{4,5}. Compared with other CB[n] members, the CB[7] host has elicited much attention because of its superior solubility in aqueous solution and remarkable capability to form host-guest complexes with organic guest molecules.

Palmatine (PAL, Fig. 1) is a natural isoquinoline alkaloid⁶. The aqueous solution of PAL exhibits weak native fluorescence. However, in the preliminary studies, the fluorescence of PAL in aqueous solution was observed to be greatly enhanced in the presence of CB[7]⁷.

Fig. 1. The structures of CB[7], PAL, CLP.

Clorprenaline (CLP, Fig. 1) is a β -agonist that was originally used as a therapeutic treatment for asthma. CLP is one of the most powerful bronchodilators currently available, and is the mainstay of initial treatment for acute exacerbation of asthma. It can be used to treat pulmonary diseases in humans and animals⁸⁻¹¹. Meanwhile, CLP is used as a doping agent among athletes to improve strength and performance¹². This compound is also well known for its ability to promote animal growth and increase muscle tissue when fed to farm animals¹³⁻¹⁵. However, meat products obtained from these animals may pose potential risks related to adverse cardiovascular and central nervous system effects¹⁶. Thus, CLP is banned in many countries and communities, such as in China, the European Union and the International Olympic Committee¹⁷. Considering the extensive application and toxic effects of CLP, a rapid, simple, and highly sensitive method to determine CLP in aqueous solution is highly desirable. A number of assays have been reported to determine CLP, including GC¹⁸, HPLC¹⁹, LC/MS²⁰ and IC²¹.

Results and discussion

The fluorescence spectra of PAL in the presence of CB[7] :

CB[7] is spectroscopically inert in aqueous solution, the aqueous solution of PAL has weak native fluorescence, and the maximum excitation and emission wavelengths are at 235 nm and 370 nm, respectively. However, when CB[7] was added to the aqueous solution of PAL, a significant increase in fluorescence intensity was observed, and accompanied by a red shift of emission wavelengths from 370 nm to 495 nm. The changes in the features of the fluorescence spectra of the solutions are attributed to the formation of an inclusion complex between PAL and CB[7]⁷.

The fluorescence quenching of CB[7]-PAL by CLP :

Significant quenching of fluorescence intensity of CB[7]-PAL complex with the addition of CLP was observed. The fluorescence spectra of CB[7]-PAL complex, in the presence of different concentrations of CLP, are shown in Fig. 2. Fluorescence intensity decreased with increased clorprenaline concentration, which is likely due to the competition between CLP and PAL molecules for occupancy of the CB[7] cavity. Parts of the PAL molecule can be expelled from the cavity of CB[7] by the

Fig. 2. Fluorescence spectra of CB[7]-PAL complex in the presence of CLP in 1.0 mM HCl aqueous solution with $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 343$ nm. The concentrations of CLP ($\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$): (a) 0; (b) 0.5; (c) 1.0; (d) 1.5; (e) 2.0. $C_{\text{CB}[7]} = 8.0 \mu\text{M}$, $C_{\text{PAL}} = 8.0 \mu\text{M}$.

introduction of CLP, thereby reducing the fluorescence intensity of CB[7]-PAL complex because of the formation of a new inclusion complex between CB[7] and CLP.

Apparent association constant and stoichiometry :

The addition of a non-fluorescent host (H) results in the formation of 1 : 1 host-guest inclusion complexes (H-G) which, in turn, enhances the fluorescence of the guest (G). The value of the enhanced fluorescence is dependent on the concentration of the added H^{22,23}, as shown in the following equation :

$$F/F_0 = 1 + (F_\infty/F_0 - 1) \frac{[H]K}{(1 + [H]K)} \quad (1)$$

where F_0 is the fluorescence intensity of G in the absence of H, F is the observed fluorescence intensity at each H concentration tested, F_∞ is the enhancement when 100% of G is complexed, and K is the equilibrium association constant for the 1 : 1 complexation.

$$K = \frac{[\text{H} - \text{G}]}{[\text{H}][\text{G}]} \quad (3)$$

The 1 : 1 complexation (and, hence, the applicability of eq. (1)) can be confirmed from the double reciprocal plot of $1/(F - F_0)$ versus $1/[\text{H}]$. The plot will be linear if only 1 : 1 complexation occurs and will be nonlinear if higher-order complexes also form.

In the interaction between CB[7] and PAL, the equilibrium reaction is as follows :

The equilibrium association constant is defined as follows :

$$K_{\text{CB[7]-PAL}} = \frac{[\text{CB[7] - PAL}]}{[\text{CB[7]}][\text{PAL}]} \quad (5)$$

Fig. 3 shows the enhancement of the PAL fluorescence as a function of added CB[7]. The inset shows the linear double reciprocal plot ($r = 0.998$), confirming the 1 : 1 stoichiometry of the complex. The solid line shows the best fit of the data to eq. (1) using the nonlinear least squares method. Four such trials were performed, yielding average values of $K_{\text{CB[7]-PAL}} = (8.02 \pm 0.76) \times 10^5 \text{ M}^{-1}$.

Fig. 3. Fluorescence enhancement of the fluorescence of a 2.0 μM solution of PAL as a function of added CB[7] in 1.0 mM HCl aqueous solution with $\lambda_{\text{ex}}/\lambda_{\text{em}} = 343/495 \text{ nm}$; the solid line shows the best fit of the data to eq. (1). The inset shows the linear double reciprocal plot indicating 1 : 1 complexation.

In the interaction between CB[7] and CLP, the equilibrium equation is as follows :

The equilibrium association constant is defined as follows :

$$K_{\text{CB[7]-CLP}} = \frac{[\text{CB[7] - CLP}]}{[\text{CB[7]}][\text{CLP}]} \quad (7)$$

When CLP was added to the aqueous solution of CB[7]-

PAL complex, equilibriums (4) and (6) coexist in the solution. Thus, combining (4) and (6) gives the following equilibrium equation :

The equilibrium association constant is defined as follows :

$$K = \frac{K_{\text{CB[7]-CLP}}}{K_{\text{CB[7]-PAL}}} = \frac{[\text{CB[7] - CLP}][\text{PAL}]}{[\text{CB[7] - PAL}][\text{CLP}]} \quad (9)$$

Wagner studied eq. (1) and reported that it applies whether the fluorescence being measured is that of the guest or the host²⁴. In addition, eq. (10) applies to the measurement of fluorescence quenching, as opposed to fluorescence enhancement²⁵, C is the concentration of the CB[7]-PAL probe. In the present study, the CB[7]-PAL complex was considered the host molecule. Thus, eq. (1) can also be applied to the quenching of CB[7]-PAL complexes (host) fluorescence with the addition of CLP (guest). Eq. (1) can be used to determine the equilibrium association constant K (eq. (9)) from the fluorescence titration data of F/F_0 at a fixed CB[7]-PAL concentration as a function of CLP concentration.

$$F/F_0 = 1 + (F_\infty/F_0 - 1) \frac{[\text{H}]K}{(C + [\text{H}]K)} \quad (10)$$

Fig. 4 shows the fluorescence quenching of CB[7]-PAL complexes with the addition of CLP. The inset shows the

Fig. 4. Fluorescence suppression of the fluorescence of CB[7]-PAL complex as a function of added CLP in 1.0 mM HCl aqueous solution with $\lambda_{\text{ex}}/\lambda_{\text{em}} = 343/495 \text{ nm}$; the solid line shows the best fit of the data to eq. (1). The inset shows the linear double reciprocal plot indicating 1 : 1 complexation. $C_{\text{CB[7]}} = C_{\text{PAL}} = 7.0 \mu\text{M}$.

linear double reciprocal plot ($r = 0.999$), indicating the formation of a 1 : 1 host-guest inclusion complex between CLP and CB[7]. The solid line shows the best fit of the data to eq. (1). Four such trials were performed, yielding average values of $K = (6.40 \pm 0.84) \text{ M}^{-1}$. The association constant value of $K_{\text{CB[7]-CLP}}$ (eq. (7)) can be calculated according to eq. (9) : $K_{\text{CB[7]-CLP}} = (5.13 \pm 0.56) \times 10^6 \text{ M}^{-1}$. The value is large, indicating very strong host-guest interactions with excellent size and shape matches. A comparison of $K_{\text{CB[7]-PAL}}$ with $K_{\text{CB[7]-CLP}}$ obviously results in $K_{\text{CB[7]-CLP}} > K_{\text{CB[7]-PAL}}$. Thus, CLP shows stronger binding with CB[7] than PAL. Accordingly, considering the thermodynamic factor only, the PAL molecule can be expelled from the CB[7] cavity by the CLP molecules.

Effect of PAL concentration on the fluorescence intensity of CB[7]-PAL complex :

The effect of varying PAL concentrations on the fluorescence intensity of CB[7]-PAL complex was studied. The concentration of PAL was varied from 1.0 μM to 12.0 μM . The fluorescence intensity of CB[7]-PAL complex was gradually enhanced as PAL concentration increased until it reached the maximum inclusion equilibrium at CB[7] saturation. In the present paper, PAL served as a fluorescent probe; thus, determining the proper concentration was crucial. If the PAL concentration is too low, the sensitivity of the probe will also be low. Conversely, a very high concentration may not help determine the optimum detection limit of the analyte. Taking everything into consideration, the optimal PAL concentration was 8.0 μM .

Influence of pH :

The effect of pH on ΔF was studied over the pH range of 1.0 to 12.0. The results indicate that ΔF is maximum and almost constant in the pH range of 1.0 to 7.0. However, ΔF significantly decreased with further increases in pH. The reason is that alkali cations are readily coordinated to the carbonyl-fringed portals of CB[7] in alkaline medium. Binding of the alkali cation lowers the rate constant of the ingress of organic guests²⁶. Results show that the presence of sodium salts in alkaline medium lowers not only the equilibrium constant of PAL binding with CB[7] but also the fluorescence quantum yield. Hence, using hydrochloric acid, the pH was adjusted to 3.0, which was the desired pH for all subsequent experiments.

Influence of temperature and reaction time :

The effect of temperature on ΔF was examined within 10 °C to 80 °C. All formed complexes were stable up to 35 °C. Above 35 °C, the fluorescence intensity greatly decreased due to the dissociation of the complexes at high temperatures. Hence, all subsequent measurements were performed at room temperature.

In addition, ΔF reached a maximum within 10 min after CLP was added and remained constant for at least 5 h. Hence, the standard reaction condition was set to room temperature for 10 min.

The response mechanism of the fluorescent probe :

PAL exhibits weak fluorescence emission in aqueous solution because the isoquinoline and the substituted benzene rings in PAL are not on the same plane. This configuration prevents a conjugated system from being formed. When CB[7] was added into the aqueous solution of PAL, the electrostatic attraction between the positive charge of the heterocyclic nitrogen of PAL and the high electron density of the carbonyl oxygens of the macrocycle was induced. The apolar part of PAL can penetrate into the host cavity. Inside the cavity, the degree of freedom of motion of the PAL molecule is reduced, thus also reducing the probability of radiationless transition. At the same time, the cavity can shield the excited single state of PAL from probable quenching processes that usually occur in aqueous solutions.

Molecular modeling calculations were optimized at the B3LYP/6-31G(d)²⁷ level of density functional theory²⁸ using the Gaussian 03 program. Results confirmed the partial inclusion of CLP in the hydrophobic cavity of CB[7] (Fig. 5). In the energy-minimized structure, the benzene ring is embedded in the CB[7] cavity, and the nitrogen atom is located in the vicinity of a carbonyl-laced portal. The photochemical property of PAL is strongly dependent on its local microenvironment. The addition of CLP caused PAL to lose its protection in the CB[7] hydrophobic cavity, thus resulting in reduced PAL fluorescence intensity.

The formation of CB[7]-PAL complex had been confirmed by ¹H NMR spectroscopy²⁹. Fig. 6a shows the ¹H NMR spectra of CB[7]-CLP complex. The results of the ¹H NMR experiments are consistent with the theoretical structures of the complex. Compared with the proton reso-

Fig. 5. Energy-minimized structure of CB[7]-CLP complex in the ground state using balls and tubes for the rendering of atoms. Color codes : CLP, green; CB[7], oxygen, red; nitrogen, blue; carbon, gray; hydrogen, white.

nances of the unbound CLP molecules (Fig. 6b), the signals of H₁, H₂, H₃, H₄, H₅ and H₆ protons of the bound CLP significantly shifted upfield, this behavior is characteristic of this part of the molecule encapsulated in the CB[7] cavity. And the signals of H₇, H₈ and H₉ protons of the bound CLP experienced downfield chemical shifts, which is characteristic of the protons of this part of the molecule located just outside the carbonyl portal of the CB[7] host³⁰. These results are consistent with the foregoing discussion.

In summary, combination of hydrophobic interaction of the cavity of CB[7], ion-dipole interaction between the carbonyl portal of CB[7] and N⁺ ion (of PAL and CLP), and hydrogen bonding interaction leads to the formation of host-guest complex. Because of the excellent size and shape matches, CLP bound with CB[7] more tightly than PAL.

Effect of interfering substances :

To evaluate the potential effect of foreign species on the determination of CLP at 1.00 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$, a systematic study was carried out. A 3000-fold mass in excess of each substance over CLP was first tested. When interference occurred, the ratio was progressively reduced until the interference ceased. The tolerance limit was defined as the ratio of the concentration of the foreign species to that of CLP which resulted in an error of less than $\pm 5\%$. The results (Table 1) showed that this method had high selectivity.

Calibration graph and sensitivity :

Under the optimum experimental conditions described above, a linear relationship between ΔF and the CLP concentrations was obtained in the range of 0.016–2.0 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$. A correlation coefficient of 0.9995 and a detection limit of 0.0053 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ were also determined.

Fig. 6. ¹H NMR spectra (600 MHz) of CB[7]-CLP complex (a), CLP (b).

Table 1. Effect of interference (tolerance error $\pm 5.0\%$)

Tolerance ratio in mass	Interference
3000	Starch, glucose, sucrose, lactose, sorbitol, mannitol, boracic acid, hexane diacid
2000	Methyl cellulose
1500	Gelatin, glycin
1000	Sodium hydroxymethyl cellulose
500	Sodium carboxymethyl cellulose
100	NH_4^+ , Na^+ , K^+
50	Mg^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , Fe^{2+}
0.2	Alanine, cysteine, cystine, phenylalanine, valine
5	Cetirizine dihydrochloride, chlorphenamine maleate, ketotifen
3	Cyproheptadine

The linear regression equation obtained was $\Delta F = 4046.1C - 21.4$. To our knowledge, usage of the spectral method for the determination of CLP has not been reported yet. Compared with other methods for the determination of CLP, including GC¹⁸, HPLC¹⁹, LC/MS²⁰ and IC²¹, the proposed method has slightly lower sensitivity, but is the most convenient analytical technique, owing to its inherent simplicity and high availability.

Analytical application :

The proposed fluorescent probe was applied in the determination of CLP in pharmaceutical preparations. Ten tablets of CLP were carefully pulverized. From this powder, an equivalent of 10 mg of CLP was accurately weighed, placed inside a 100 mL calibrated flask, dissolved in 20 mL water, and sonicated for 3 min. The resulting solution was diluted to volume with water. The first 10 mL of the filtrate was discarded, after which 10 mL of the remaining filtered sample solution was diluted to 100 mL with double-distilled water. Further dilutions were performed to obtain the sample solutions using the same testing methods as described in experimental procedure. The results are presented in Table 2. The relative standard deviations obtained from the proposed method were less than 1.00%. Moreover, the *t*- and *F*-tests showed that the proposed method had good precision and accuracy. The proposed fluorescent probe was also tested in recovery studies of CLP in human urine samples, where varying amounts of CLP were added to diluted (100-fold) urine samples. The results (Table 3) suggest that the probe

Table 2. Analytical results and recovery tests of CLP in pharmaceutical formulation

Drugs	Label claim (mg/grain)	Fluorescent probe method		
		Found (mg/grain)	Equivalent nominal content (%) \pm S.D. ^a	Recovery (%) \pm S.D. ^a
CLP ^b	5	4.91 (<i>t</i> , 1.65; <i>F</i> , 3.18)	98.20 \pm 0.70	98.93 \pm 0.65
CLP ^b	10	9.81 (<i>t</i> , 1.54; <i>F</i> , 2.92)	98.10 \pm 0.71	98.41 \pm 0.69

^aAverage of five determination (The tabulated values of *t* and *F* at the 95% confidence limit are *t* = 2.31 and *F* = 6.39).

^bCLP Tablets (Jiangsu Chenpai Pharmaceutical Co., Ltd, Haimen, China).

Table 3. Fluorimetric determination of CLP in spiked urine (*n* = 5)

Samples	Amount added (mg mL ⁻¹)	Amount found (mg mL ⁻¹)	Recovery (%) \pm S.D. ^a
Urine 1	0.50	0.47	94.00 \pm 1.2
Urine 2	0.75	0.76	101.33 \pm 0.91
Urine 3	1.00	0.96	96.00 \pm 0.94

can be used for the determination of CLP with satisfactory recoveries of 94.00–101.33%.

Experimental

Apparatus :

Fluorescence spectra were obtained with an Agilent Technologies Cary Eclipse fluorescence spectrofluorometer (Agilent, Australia) equipped with a pulsed lamp. The slit widths of both excitation and emission monochromators were set to 5 nm. The fluorescence spectra were recorded at a scan rate of 600 nm min⁻¹. All measurements were performed using a standard 10 mm path-length quartz cell at 25.0 °C \pm 0.5 °C. The pH values were measured using a pH-3 TC digital precision pH meter (Shanghai, China). ¹H NMR spectra were obtained using a Bruker DRX-600 MHz spectrometer (Switzerland) in D₂O.

Reagents and chemicals :

PAL and CLP were obtained from the Chinese National Institute for the Control of Pharmaceutical and Biological Products (Beijing, China) without further treatment. CLP was dissolved in double-distilled water to prepare stock standard solutions of 100 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$. PAL was dissolved in double-distilled water to prepare stock solu-

tions with final concentration of 1.0 mM. CB[7] was prepared and characterized according to reported procedure². CB[7] stock solution of 1.0 mM was prepared by dissolving CB[7] in double-distilled water. Stock standard solutions were stable for several weeks at room temperature. Standard working solutions were prepared by diluting the stock standard solutions with double-distilled water before use. All other chemicals were of analytical reagent grade, and double-distilled water was used throughout the procedure.

Experimental procedure :

0.8 mL solution of 0.1 mM CB[7] was poured into a 10 mL colorimetric flask, to which 0.9 mL of 0.1 mM PAL solution and 1.0 mL of 0.01 M hydrochloric acid were also added. Suitable amounts of CLP solution were then sequentially added to the flask. The mixture was diluted to volume with double-distilled water and shaken for 15 min at room temperature. The fluorescence intensity values of the solution ($F_{\text{PAL-CB[7]-CLP}}$) and the blank solution ($F_{\text{PAL-CB[7]}}$) were measured at 495 nm using an excitation wavelength of 343 nm.

Conclusions

In summary, the fluorescent probe system CB[7]-PAL complex is successfully used to detect CLP in aqueous solution, which exhibits rapid response, high sensitivity and high selectivity. The general concept used in this approach is based on the competition between CLP and PAL for occupancy of the CB[7] cavity, resulting in the ΔF of the CB[7]-PAL supramolecular complex. The detection limit is as low as 0.0053 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ for CLP. In addition, the proposed method is successfully applied to determine CLP in its pharmaceutical dosage forms and urine samples. The results provide a new approach for potential medical and biological implications. This method can also be used as a fluorescence sensor to detect non-fluorescent or weakly fluorescent substances. Related studies are underway in our laboratory.

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